

Propositions

accompanying the dissertation

AUGMENTED FINE-GRAINED DEFECT PREDICTION FOR CODE REVIEW

by

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1. The state of the art of defect prediction is not ready for use by developers in their day-to-day work. [This thesis]
2. Code comments written by open-source developers are more precise and descriptive than those written by industrial developers. [This thesis]
3. Just-in-time defect prediction models can help developers in locating half of the defects by inspecting only a quarter of the lines of code in committed files. [This thesis]
4. Conferences and journals must desk reject work without proper replication packages.
5. Professors in academia should be primarily researchers and teachers to spread their knowledge and, only in the second instance, entrepreneurs in search of funds.
6. To compete with the worldwide market and to facilitate cross-country communication, European members should vote in favor of adopting a single common language.
7. Developing good software is an art that demands the same creativity and effort required to create idyllic poems; therefore, technical universities should impose art classes.
8. Pure research must primarily address social issues and later meet industrial needs.
9. People that have been to Venice, Florence, and Milan should not affirm to have visited Italy.

These propositions are regarded as opposable and defensible, and have been approved as such by the promoters prof. dr. A. van Deursen, dr. A. Becchelli.